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Paper Chromatographic Separations of Some Metallic Ions using Penicillins

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SEPARATIONS of certain metal ions, important for the composition of certain special alloys, have been affected using solutions of penicillins as the mobile phase. This underlines, in continuation of our previous communications¹⁻⁴ (related with the study of the potentiality of penicillins as analytical reagent) utility of the same as chromatographic reagent.

A.R. grade metallic salts were used to prepare 0.1M solutions of the metallic ions. The paper used in the study was Whatman No. 1 chromatographic paper. Fe(III), Cu(II), Ag(I) and Cr(III) were detected with the help of the characteristic colours they give with penicillins [Fe(III), reddish brown; Cr(III), greyish green; Ag(I), pale and Cu(II), olive green], while the other metallic ions were detected using usual spotting reagents⁵.

The metallic ions tried in this study were Be (II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Pb(II), Cr(III), Al(III), Fe(III), Ag(I), Mo(VI) and W(VI).

Impregnated papers were prepared by soaking the paper in 2% (W/V) aqueous solutions of Na or K salts of penicillin - G (PG) or penicillin - V (PV) and drying them at room temperature in a dust free chamber.

The mobile phase used with the plain paper include 0.02 M and 0.01 M aqueous solutions of Na/

K-PG and -PV and 1 : 1 mixtures of 0.01 M aqueous penicillins (PG or PV) with ethanol and acetone; while pure organic solvents including a range of polar solvents with donor properties - ethanol, acetone, chloroform and ethyl acetate - were used with the impregnated papers.

Chromatograms using both descending and disc techniques were prepared and Rf-values noted.

Results and Discussion

A comparison of Rf-values obtained in this study indicate that effective separations of certain closely resembling metallic ions (some of them very important for the composition of certain technologically important alloys) can be affected using aqueous solutions of penicillins-G or -V on filter paper strips by descending method. While, the results obtained with radial development technique⁶, using plain and impregnated paper discs showed, although the mobilities of metal ions were found faster on plain papers with the use of aqueous solutions of the penicillins, better separations with least diffusion were obtained using 1 : 1 mixtures (V/V) of the aqueous solutions of PG or PV with ethanol or acetone. On impregnated papers while, chloroform and ethyl acetate failed to give mobility to the metal ions, ethanol and acetone could give sufficient mobilities of the ions and effect separations.

The faster mobilities of metal ions affecting better separations with the use of solutions of penicillins (pure or in 1 : 1 mixtures with ethanol or acetone) can be understood in the light of following mechanism. On plain papers the metal ions in the form of aquo-cations are absorbed with the formation of ion associated metal cellulose bond⁷. On irrigating the paper with solutions of penicillins, the penicillin molecules form complexes with the metal cations displacing the coordinated aquo-molecules partially or wholly. Thus the metal ions get desorbed and are washed away with the solvent. A similar mechanism works on impregnated paper, where the presence of penicillin molecules on the paper shields the metal ion from forming ion associated bond with cellulose. During spotting of the metal ion, the penicillin molecules present on paper form metal-ligand complex with the metal ion. The metal ion thus remains in desorbed state, which is then washed away with the solvent due to its solvating effect. The poor or no mobilities of metallic ions with chloroform and ethyl acetate was found related with the insolubilities of the metal penicillin adducts in these solvents; ethanol and acetone due to their sufficient solvating effect to these metal adducts could give faster mobilities and more effective separations. The separational possibilities of some of the closely resembling ions are summarised in the Table 1.

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TABLE 1—SEPARATIONAL POSSIBILITIES OF IONS USING PENICILLINS

Temp. 30°, Time 60 mins. Paper—Whatman No. 1

	Ions Separated	Method	Solvents	Ions Separated	Method	Solvent
1.	Be ⁺⁺ , Mg ⁺⁺	a	1,2	13.	Fe ⁺⁺ , Fe ⁺⁺⁺	a 1,2
2.	Be ⁺⁺ , Al ⁺⁺⁺	a	1,2	14.	Al ⁺⁺⁺ , Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Cr ⁺⁺⁺	a 1,2
3.	Be ⁺⁺ , Ca ⁺⁺	a	1,2	15.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Mo ⁶⁺ , W ⁶⁺	a 1,2
4.	Zn ⁺⁺ , Mn ⁺⁺	a	1,2	16.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Cr ⁺⁺⁺ , Mo ⁶⁺ , W ⁶⁺	a 1,2
5.	Pb ⁺⁺ , Zn ⁺⁺	a	1,2	17.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺ , Ni ⁺⁺	a 1,2
6.	Ag ⁺ , Zn ⁺⁺	a	1,2			b 1,2,3,4
7.	Ag ⁺ , Pb ⁺⁺	a	2			d 7,8
8.	Ag ⁺ , Cu ⁺⁺	a	1	18.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺ , Ni ⁺⁺ , Cr ⁺⁺⁺	a 1,2
9.	Cu ⁺⁺ , Mn ⁺⁺	a	1,2			b 1,2
		b	2,3,5,6	19.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺ , Ni ⁺⁺ , Cu ⁺⁺	a 1,2
		c	7,8			b 2
		d	7,8			d 7
10.	Cu ⁺⁺ , Cr ⁺⁺⁺	a	1	20.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺ , Ni ⁺⁺ , Mn ⁺⁺	a 1
		b	2,3,4,5,6			d 8
		c	7,8	21.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺ , Ni ⁺⁺ , Mn ⁺⁺ , Cu ⁺⁺	a 1
		d	8	22.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺ , Ni ⁺⁺ , Cu ⁺⁺ , Mn ⁺⁺ , Cr ⁺⁺⁺	a 1
11.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Mn ⁺⁺	a	1,2	23.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺ , Ni ⁺⁺ , Cu ⁺⁺ , Mn ⁺⁺ , Ag ⁺	a 1
		b	1,2,3,5,6	24.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺ , Ni ⁺⁺ , Cu ⁺⁺ , Zn ⁺⁺	a 2
		c	7,8	25.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺ , Ni ⁺⁺ , Cu ⁺⁺ , Zn ⁺⁺ , Ag ⁺	a 2
		d	7,8			
12.	Mn ⁺⁺ , Co ⁺⁺	a	1,2			
		b	2,3,5,6			
		c	7			
		d	7,8			

Solvents :

1. 0.01M aq. Soln. of PG ;
2. 0.01M aq. Soln. of PV ;
3. 1 : 1 Mixt. of 1 and Ethanol ;
4. 1 : 1 Mixt. of 1 and Acetone ;
5. 1 : 1 Mixt. of 2 and Ethanol ;
6. 1 : 1 Mixt. of 2 and Acetone ;
7. Ethanol ;
8. Acetone.

Methods :

- a—Descending, On plain paper ;
 b—Disc, On plain paper ;
 c—Disc, On PG impregnated paper ;
 d— Disc, On PV impregnated paper.

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